

ABSTRACT

Web based resources are playing an important place in the academic life of the students in our country. The students use the website for getting the primary information with regard to any educational institution. University websites are the gateways for the students. The students are empowered to get the information virtually without visiting the campus physically. The students get information with regard to admissions, examinations, results etc. Therefore, it become the need of the hour to conduct a website analysis of the university's websites. The aim and objective of the present study was to analyse the content of the websites of the Universities situated in Gujarat State. A Checklist in this regard was used by the investigator to conduct the website analysis. Sixty five universities are there in Gujarat, but the present study was delimited to the four Agricultural Universities of Gujarat State.

Keywords : Website analysis, University Website, World Wide Web, Higher Education.

Introduction

The use of websites in educational contexts is increasing day by day. There is a great impact of technology on the educational system. The technology has increased the usage of websites in educational contexts in India. The delivery of content through websites is possible due to the World Wide Web. It serves as a base for making the content available to the beneficiaries in no time. In today's era there is a great demand for education in various countries. There are various efforts done by the between many countries to collaborate with other universities virtually. The coordination between universities is possible due to the World Wide Web. The Web has made our life easy and we can freely collaborate. Various universities are there who are using the Web as a communication tool. The Website that works on the principles of the World Wide Web caters to the needs of the students virtually. The students get access to various things online with a single click. The website becomes the primary gateway for the students. It caters to the various needs of the students. The students get admission, results related information from the websites. The World Wide Web (WWW) can be considered as the main source for getting academic or research based information and thus enables us to test new methods online like conducting an analysis of the content of the website (Madhuri, Babu and Ramesh, 2010).

Website

The internet has become a common place for us to surf the web pages of any particular websites. It gives us a lot of information within seconds. The information available on the internet is generated from a multiple sources and is organised in such a way that users are given step by step procedures to access the information. The files are organised, and web pages are created which ultimately form a website.

Hence, we can say that a website is a collection of web pages that contain text, images and all other multimedia information that is presented to the users in an easy method. All Internet-enabled websites form the World Wide Web (WWW). A website is a group of related web pages, images, videos or other digital resources accessed through a unique Uniform Resource Locator.

Higher Education Websites

Higher education websites need great attention in terms of their development. The website must appeal to

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the university's commercial interests, which are primarily the sources of presenting their objectives to the visitors and especially to those visitors who are interested in seeking information. Baka and Leyni (2015) in a related study revealed that top rank universities websites are more visible and accessible as compared to the other website.

The Higher Education website aims to facilitate their prospective students and scholars by providing the proper guidelines on the website to help them accordingly. Nevertheless, of equal importance, a university website should at least contain that type of information that the students and its faculty members are in need of. Information like the complexities of curriculum choices and the information about the daily events and procedures that happen within a busy university campus. Therefore, usability is considered the key credential of effective higher education website design. Maintaining institutional repositories, open access, and collaboration with other universities, online communication etc. help to increase the visibility of the particular website (Sujithai and Jeyshankar, 2013).

Rationale of the Study

The World Wide Web connects people via the internet and makes millions of web resources accessible for them. The website is the collection of related documents. The website is considered as the first gate way of students towards a particular educational institution. Today's the access of the internet is common. So the popularity of the websites has been increased. The millions of new web pages are designed daily. Many of these are designed and developed by the people who give little attention to the fact that how this information will be used and who will use. It would be very beneficial to provide guidelines and frameworks for making the pleasing user experiences in such systems. The web content available on the University website should as such that fullfills the need of its users. Hence there is an immense need to conduct the webometric study of the university website.

Objective of the Study

To study the web content of University Websites

Method and Procedure

Population

As per the data available on the online portal of Gujarat Education Department, Gujarat has a total number of 65 Universities that includes 18 State Universities, 04 Agricultural Universities, 03 Central Universities, 02 private aided Universities, 32 private Universities and 06 institute of National Importance. Hence all the 65 Universities constitute the population of the study.

Sample

Based on the population, the investigator selected four agricultural Universities as the sample of the study. These four Universities are mentioned below along with their website address :

Table 1
Name of Universities along with their website address

S. No.	Name of the University	Website Address
1	Anand Agricultural University	www.aau.in
2	Navsari Agricultural University	www.nau.in
3	Sardarkrushinagar Dantiwada Agricultural University	www.sdau.edu.in
4	Junagarh Agricultural University	www.jau.in

Tool

The investigator developed a self-made checklist consisting of 17 items. The items were framed according to the following category:

Table 2
Dimensions of Checklist

Category	Item No.	Total No of Items
Web Design	1,2, 3, 4,6, 13,14	7
Website Language	5, 7,	2
Contact Details	8, 9, 17	3
Introduction about University	15,16	2
Website Updation & Visitor count	11,12	2
Students section	10	1

Technique of Analysis and Interpretation

For the analysis and interpretation of the data, the investigator used the technique of content analysis.

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Delimitations

- The study is delimited to Universities of Gujarat State.
- The study is delimited to four agricultural universities of Gujarat.

Result and Discussion

Table 3

Checklist for Analysis of University Websites

S. No.	Question	AAU	NAU	SDAU	JAU
1	The interface of the website is attractive.	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
2	The website is easily accessible through search engines.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
3	The website URL is easy to remember.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
4	The website has a smooth navigation.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
5	The text on the website is easily readable.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
6	The website has an events webpage for latest happenings in the University.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
7	The website has Multilanguage support.	No	No	No	No
8	The website contains a telephone directory of all the University employees.	No	No	No	No
9	The website contains the dedicated profile details of all the faculty members.	Yes	No	No	Yes

10	The website contains a feedback form for students.	Yes	No	No	No
11	The website mentions the visitor counter.	Yes	No	No	Yes
12	The website Updation is being made on regular basis.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
13	The website has a dedicated examination result webpage.	No	Yes	No	No
14	The result web page contains the latest examination result.	No	Yes	No	No
15	The website has a dedicated webpage regarding the introduction of the university.	Yes	No	No	Yes
16	The website contains an introductory video about the Universities.	No	No	No	No
17	The website mentions its full address and contact details on the contact us webpage.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Website Interface and Access through Search Engines

The website interface of all the four Agricultural Universities is attractive. The Website of Anand Agricultural University has a static background image with a photo slide of the University on the Homepage. The website is designed with multiple colors that gives a decent look to its interface. Similarly the Website of Navsari Agricultural University also carries a photo slide show of University but the interface is to some extent not attractive. The website has a static plain background image. The website interface of Sardar

krushinagar Dantiwada Agricultural University is quite attractive. With a photo slideshow and a static coloured background image, the interface of the website is giving a new look to its website. Similarly, the website interface of Junagarh Agricultural University is also good but lacks in the background image setting.

While search the all the four website through popular search engines like Google & Yahoo, all the four universities were easily accessible and were able to be find through the search engines.

Website URL and Smooth Navigation

The website URL of all the four Universities is very easy to remember. The website URL consists of at least 3-5 words which is very much easy to remember. Regarding the smooth navigation of the websites, all the four websites are having a smooth navigation. It is very much easy to switch to page on the website.

Website text and Events Webpage

The websites of all the four Universities contains the text which is readable and all the website contain an events webpage on their website where the latest happening and the upcoming events in the University can be found.

Website Multilingual Support and availability of University Telephone Directory

The website of all the four agricultural Universities do not have multilingual support nor do they have any kind of telephone directory available on their website. The Website interface of Anand Agricultural University, Navsari Agricultural University and Junagarh Agricultural University contain text in English in one side and on the other side, Gujarati language text can be found. The website even does not have support to Google translator for translating the Gujarati language into English or some other language. Similarly, the Website of S. D. Agricultural University is mainly having English language as their default website language and the website doesn't have support to Google Translator as well. Regarding the availability of telephone directory on the website, all the four agricultural universities are lacking behind.

Availability of Profile details of faculty members and feedback from for students

The website of Anand and Junagarh Agricultural University have maintained dedicated profile details of all the faculty members on their website. However, the website of Navsari and S. D. Agricultural University have not updated the profile details of their faculty members on their website.

With reference to the availability of feedback form, the Anand Agricultural University has maintained feedback form link under 'Contact Us' web page. However Junagarh, Navsari and S. D. Agricultural University haven't kept any feedback form for students on their website.

Website Visitor Counter and Updation

The website of Anand and Junagarh Agricultural University have maintained website visitor counter on their website. The Anand Agricultural University has put the visitor counter badge at the bottom of their website. Similarly, Junagarh Agricultural University has put the visitor counter badge on the left down side of their website. However, the website of Navsari and S. D. Agricultural University have not kept any visitor counter on their website.

Regarding the website Updation, all the websites are being updated timely as look like from the homepages of the websites.

Website result Webpage with latest exam results

The Website of Navsari Agricultural University contains a dedicated webpage for examination results on its homepage that is updated with latest results. However the researcher fails to find any such thing on the official websites of Junagarh, Anand and S. D. Agricultural University.

Website Introductory Webpage and Video

The websites of Navsari and Junagarh Agricultural University have maintained an introductory webpage about the University on their website. However, the author fails to find any such webpage on the websites of Anand and S. D. Agricultural University.

While analysing the website of all the four universities, the researcher fails to find an introductory video about the University.

University Contact Details on Website

While analysing the website of the Agricultural Universities, the researcher found that all the four universities have updated their contact details in the 'Contact us' webpage including official address, email, Telephone number and Fax.

Findings of the Study

1. The website interface of all the four Agricultural Universities are attractive and all the websites are accessible through various search engines like Google and Yahoo.
2. The website URL of all the four Universities is very easy to remember and all the website has a smooth navigation across different web pages.
3. The websites of all the four Agricultural Universities contain the text which is readable and all the website contain an events webpage on their website where the latest happening and the upcoming events in the University can be found.
4. The website of all the four agricultural Universities do not have multilingual support nor do they have any kind of telephone directory available on their website.
5. The website of Anand and Junagarh Agricultural University have maintained dedicated profile details of all the faculty members on their website. However, the website of Navsari and S. D. Agricultural University has not updated the profile details of their faculty members on their website.
6. With reference to the availability of feedback form, the Anand Agricultural University has maintained feedback form link under 'Contact Us' web page. However Junagarh, Navsari and S. D. Agricultural University haven't kept any feedback form for students on their website.
7. The website of Anand and Junagarh Agricultural University have maintained website visitor counter on their website. However, the website of Navsari and S. D. Agricultural University have not kept any visitor counter on their website. Regarding the website Updation, all the four Agricultural websites are being updated on regular basis.

8. The Website of Navsari Agricultural University contains a dedicated webpage for examination results on its homepage that is updated with latest results. However the researcher fails to find any such web page on the websites of Junagarh, Anand and S. D. Agricultural University.
9. The websites of Navsari and Junagarh Agricultural University have maintained an introductory webpage about the University on their website. However, the researcher fails to find any such webpage on the websites of Anand and S. D. Agricultural University. While analysing the website of all the four universities, the researcher fails to find an introductory video about the University.
10. While analysing the website of the Agricultural Universities, the researcher found that all the four universities has updated their contact details in the 'Contact us' webpage including official address, email, Telephone number and Fax.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations are given:

1. The website needs to be updated on regular basis.
2. There is a need to maintain a telephone directory on the website containing the telephone numbers of all the employees of the University.
3. Each educational institution must have a feedback form for students so that students can share their valuable views with university authorities.
4. The website must have multi lingual support or the IT team should enable the Google Translator badge on the website.

Conclusion

Based on the study, the researcher is aware of the fact that no broad conclusion can be made. The websites of universities in Gujarat is an uncharted area of webometric research. This study presents a fair thought about the information provided by the websites of the 04 Agricultural Universities of Gujarat. These findings open the door to further studies of other new areas of the web. This study could be extended further by doing a webometric study of State, Private Aided and Central University of Gujarat State.

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state is not adequate. Therefore, there is need to make some reformation in imparting human rights education to the teacher trainees so as to equip them with knowledge, attitude and pedagogical skills to promote human rights among the students in their actual classrooms. Human rights education should be rightly placed in all the course papers especially in the pedagogical subject of science. A project on human rights education is a requisite to enhance the cognitive and affective skills of human rights among the pupil-teachers so that they can be a catalyst in the promotion of human rights culture.

References

1. Agarwal, H. O. (2018). *Human rights. Darbhanga Castel; Allahabad: Central Law Publication*
2. Fatema, M. (2019). *Comparing the level of human rights awareness between prospective teachers in the city of Aurangabad. Scholarly Research Journal for Humanity Science & English Language (7)31, 8491-8498. Retrieved from <http://oaji.net/articles/2019/1201-1558772047.pdf>*
3. Huntsoe, A. & Kapoor, K.C. (2019). *A study of human rights awareness among the postgraduate students in relation to various non-cognitive variables. International journal for research in engineering application & management, Vol. (4)10, 349-353*
4. Katoch, S. K. (2012). *Human rights awareness among secondary teacher trainees of Himachal. Retrieved from http://icdeolhpu.org/journal/Suman_Katoch.pdf*
5. Oommen, M. N. (2018). *A Study on Awareness of Human Rights among Teacher Trainees. International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology (7) 6, 6815-6856. Retrieved from http://www.ijirset.com/upload/2018/june/74_a%20study.pdf*
6. Sasikala.V&Francisca. S. (2016). *Human rights awareness among female prospective teachers. International Journal of Teacher Educational Research, 5, 3-5. Retrieved from <http://ijter.com/pdf%20files%20folder/maraug2016/p7.pdf>*
7. Singh, B. & Singh, T. (2015). *Human rights awareness among teacher trainees. Contemporary research in India, 5(3). Retrieved from <https://www.contemporaryresearchindia.net/pdf/september-2015/03.pdf>*

8. United Nations General Assembly . (1948). *Resolution adopted by the general assembly 217 A (III): Universal declaration of human rights. Retrieved from <http://www.un-documents.net/a3r217a.htm>*
9. United Nations General Assembly. (2012). *United Nations Declaration on Human Rights Education and Training. Resolution adopted by the General Assembly on 19 December 2011. Retrieved from <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/undoc/gen/n11/467/04/pdf/n1146704.pdf?openement>*

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References

1. Anand Agricultural University. Retrieved from <http://www.aau.in/>
2. Baka, A. B. A. & Leyni, N. (2015). *Webometric Study of World Class Universities Websites. Qualitative and Quantitative Methods in Libraries, 105-115. Retrieved from <http://tinyurl.com/y2f6h3gm>*
3. Chakravarty, R. & Wasan, S. (2015). *Webometric Analysis of Library Websites of Higher Educational Institutes (HEIs) of India: A Study through Google Search Engine. Journal of Library & Information Technology, 35(5), 325-329. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/y4a6rrep> Education Department, Government of Gujarat. <http://gujarat-education.gov.in/education/alluniversity.htm>*
4. Junagadh Agricultural University. Retrieved from <http://www.jau.in/> Madhuri, A. J., Babu, K. and Ramesh, P. A. (2013). *Webometric Analysis of State Universities in Andhra Pradesh: A Study. E-Library Science Research Journal, 1(7), 1-11. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/y4s7dasn>*
5. Navsari Agricultural University. Retrieved from <http://www.nau.in/>
6. Sardarkrushinagar Agricultural University. Retrieved from <http://www.sdau.edu.in/>
7. Sujithai M, Jeyshankar R. (2013). *Web Page Analysis of Indian Institute of Technologies' (IITS) Websites: A Webometric Study. International Journal of Digital Library Services, 3(1), 55-65. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/y2tecmzg>*